

Welcome to the third edition of the ENTRUST newsletter! We are excited to share with you the latest updates and initiatives from our project.

This issue covers our #WomenInScience campaign, recaps our partners' 2nd plenary meeting in Eindhoven, and offers further insights into connected medical devices.

Enjoy the read!

Women in Science Campaign

In February, we joined the global #WomenInScience campaign by sharing inspiring stories from our partners. Explore these interviews to discover their valuable contributions to science and technology.

Interview with Renáta Radócz, Mandat International

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Interview with Nada El Kassem, University of Surrey

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Interview with Cristina Vladarean, SIEMENS SRL

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Interview with Barbara Guerra, PARTICLE

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Interview with Lina Giannakandropoulou, UniSystems Luxembourg SARRL

[Learn more](#)

ENTRUST 2nd Plenary Meeting in Eindhoven

In a collaborative effort towards innovation and progress, the 2nd Plenary Meeting for the ENTRUST project took place in Eindhoven on December 5-6, 2023, bringing together all project partners and marking a significant step forward in realizing the project's objectives.

[Learn more](#)

Latest from our blog

In ENTRUST project, we are working collaboratively to design and develop a Trust Management framework. A combination of software applications, methods and technologies will be used that when operating all together will have as a result to ensure trust among all the devices involved in the system where the framework is applied.

[Learn more](#)

ENTRUST welcomes a new synergies partner - Digital Health Uptake (DHU). DHU aims to facilitate the alignment of policies, strategies, instruments, and activities to advance the uptake of digital health solutions and services in Europe.

[Learn more](#)

Modern medical organizations, such as hospitals and healthcare providers, are increasingly adopting network infrastructures comprising multiple heterogeneous medical devices with varying computational capabilities and originating from different manufacturers, which may be subject to various security and trustworthiness requirements.

[Learn more](#)

Partners

